

DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORT

Abdurashid Tolibayevich Nomozov

JDPU. Teacher of the department of Theory and method of physical culture

Annotation. *This article talks about changes in sports, the processes of training athletes, and the introduction of new technologies.*

Key words: *Healthy lifestyle, physical training, technique, tactics, competitions.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассказывается об изменениях в спорте, процессах подготовки спортсменов, внедрении новых технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *Здоровый образ жизни, физическая подготовка, техника, тактика, соревнования.*

Аннотация. *Ушбу мақолада, спортчиларнинг тайёргарлик жараёнлари, янги технологияларнинг кириб келиши спортдаги ўзгаришлар ҳақида сўз юритилади.*

Таянч сўзлар: *Соғлом турмуш тарзи, жисмоний тарбия, техника, тактика, мусобақа.*

The rapid development and development of our society, the peace and abundance in the life of our people, the hard work and courage in the hearts of our independent state are evidence of the increasing progress of our independent state, including the correct systematic policy in the field of sports that can fully meet today's requirements.

Every nation has its own traditions, customs and traditions. In our country, we pay special attention to the birth of healthy offspring, the stability and strength of the family, and the educational relations between the society and relatives. Also, national values, oriental customs and healthy lifestyle are always respected.

A healthy lifestyle is first formed in the family, and the role of physical education in establishing a healthy lifestyle is very important. In particular, great attention is paid to the field of sports in order to raise a healthy generation. In this regard, as a result of the work carried out in the field of sports, we can clearly see that effective results are being achieved in protecting the spiritual void in the minds of the youth, who are the future of our country, from foreign ideas.

The policy of sports development is directly and indirectly related to the stages of the education system, in order to strengthen the special control over the health of young men and women, who are the future of our country, to form a healthy lifestyle, to attract them to sports clubs, and to introduce measures to spend their free time meaningfully. A three-stage sports holiday is being held to educate students and young people in a spirit of patriotism.

The young people selected from this stage are winning prizes at world universities and summer olympic games and are flying the flag of our country at the highest heights. This is also the result of the three-stage sports traditional holiday introduced in our country.

Sports palaces, football fields and modern equipment that meet the requirements of world standards, which are being paid attention to physical education and sports today, are a clear proof of this.

In today's sports, new technologies are actively developing, not only for television or sports competitions, but also for athletes and coaches to effectively manage sports training and to master exercise techniques. For example, in the football sport, there is a computer system for coaches that helps to calculate the technical and tactical actions of the players of their team and the players of the opposing team during the game and to manage the game.

In addition to these, technologies that determine the athlete's physical condition during training and competition are widely used in modern sports. Cardiographs and accelerometers built into watches or shoes for athletes. For tennis players, devices that indicate the force and direction of a tennis racket.

Heart rate monitors used in all sports are an example of this.

In conclusion, it can be said that currently the training processes of athletes are developing and perfecting. The introduction of new technologies has brought great changes in sports. Today's sports are very different from those of ancient Greece. The results shown by athletes no longer depend only on physical training. Inventions made in the last century have left new modern lines in the field of sports. We are so used to such devices that we consider it normal to use devices that count millimeters and milliseconds in sports.

It's not just television or showing sports competitions, but computer programs designed for athletes and coaches to effectively manage sports training and master exercise techniques are actively developing.

References:

1. Matveev L.P. Teoriya i metodika fizicheskoy kulturo'. Uchebnik dlya institutov. fiz. kulturo'. M. FiS. 1991
2. Ashmarin B.A., Zavyalov L.K., Kuramshin Yu.F. Pedagogika fizicheskoy kulturo': Uchebnoe posobie dlya studentov uchebno'x zavedeniy. SPb.; LGOU, 1999.
3. Hasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура и спорт как важный аспект в формировании личности. Форум молодых ученых. 5. 425-428.
4. Hasanov, Anvar. (2017). Физическая культура-надежда нации. Форум молодых ученых. 5. 591.
5. Yakhshilikov, S. (2023). UNAVOIDABLE CLASHES: EXPLORING THE IMPLICATIONS OF A CHINA-RUSSIA ALLIANCE ON GLOBAL GEOPOLITICS. AUSTRAL: Brazilian Journal of Strategy & International Relations, 12(23). <https://doi.org/10.22456/2238-6912.131366>